

MEDIATING ROLE OF PROSUSTAINABILITY NETWORK QUALITY IN THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY

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Abstract:

"Customer is the King", is a sentence that reminds every businessman to manage the ability to maintain customer loyalty because it will increase the company's sustainability. And maintain loyal customers so that the company remains competitive even though there are situational influences and marketing efforts from competitors that have the potential to cause switching behavior, and one of them is a marketing strategy using social media to establish relationships with customers. This study empirically examines the influence of social media on customers. Loyalty is mediated by prosustainability network quality. This study aims to fill the gap in research and develop network theory. The sample of this research is a distributor of industrial sandpaper companies in Indonesia spread over 34 provinces, and sampling is done by Simple Random Sampling. Data was collected by distributing questionnaires directly to the respondents, as many as 300 questionnaires. The statistical method used is Smart PLS. The results of this study indicate that the positive and significant Prosustainability Network Quality mediates the relationship between Social Media and Customer Loyalty, the fulfillment of aspects of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty is the ultimate goal to be achieved by every company, whether engaged in manufacturing or services. So that, further research is recommended to add a variable Customer Satisfaction.

Keywords: Social Media, Customer Loyalty, Prosustainability, Network Quality

Introduction

Today, many companies are innovating and investing to increase existing resources to maintain and increase customer loyalty. The company is always trying to get information on maintaining and increasing customer loyalty. Customer loyalty has a very important role; maintaining those means improving financial performance and maintaining the company's viability (Mahmud & Sudarmiatin, 2021). It is the main reason for a company to attract and retain customers. Those who are loyal will reduce the effort to find new customers, giving positive feedback to the organization. In addition, loyalty positively impacts profitability (Hallowell, 1996; Rowley & Dawes, 1999).

In a customer-oriented business, where companies are faced with more customers, more products, more competitors, and limited time to react in terms of understanding customers, companies have to work harder to interact with customers (Jayawarsa et al, 2021). Interaction

with customers' needs to be continuously improved in a better direction to know the wants and needs of each individual. The right time is a fact that the interaction with the customer is now ongoing. With the right channel or platform, companies can interact with customers in various ways, either in the form of direct mail or email, and telemarketing. It could be due to the development of information technology, with information technology companies looking to move from a single selling model to an ongoing sales relationship with their customers. Companies strive to understand how to build and maintain relationships with loyal customers, and find the most profitable ways to build relationships.

A recent study investigated the relationship between customer loyalty and social media engagement (Van Asperen et al., 2018). This study surveyed more than 1,000 industrial customers in Indonesia and social media engagement to measure the level of customer loyalty. The results show that using social media is directly related to increased loyalty. This study states that organizations can bring back dissatisfied customers and stakeholders through social media channels. Currently, carefully designed customer loyalty programs through social media have become an important part of marketing strategy (Chang et al., 2020). In the digital era, companies are encouraged to communicate with customers through social media and form customer loyalty. However, the effect of social media and its mechanism has not been studied further; how sellers use social media to influence customer trust and increase customer loyalty. The concept is interesting as it is assumed that loyalty can greatly value companies and customers (Yang, 2004). Existing research has shown a significant and positive influence between social media and customer loyalty mediated by customer equity drivers (Yadav & Rahman, 2017). The above findings follow other studies (Dwivedi et al., 2016; Ou et al., 2014; Vogel et al., 2008) in their literature that prominent customer equity drivers are the drivers of customer loyalty through social media.

On the other hand, the public tends to complain when something goes wrong. Now times have changed. In the past, complaints were mostly submitted by telephone; in this digital era, 65% of customers prefer to submit complaints via social media rather than call centers, because social media is more practical, at a much cheaper cost, and faster. Read by admin-marketing. The following studies show some research gaps between social media variables on customer loyalty and other independent variables. For example, Marzouk (2016) reports that the relationship between social media marketing and brand loyalty is weak and insignificant, although his study also shows that social media marketing influences the formation and expansion of brand awareness and, in turn, increases the company's sales performance. Then the offer of a conceptual model that describes the relationship between SMP (Social Media Platform) and CBL (Consumer Brand Loyalty) was obtained from Jibril et al. (2019), which conducted a study of 122 social media users affiliated with at least one online brand community, found that SMP (social media platform) only indirectly stimulated consumer-brand promise and trust (CBPT), towards CBL (consumer brand loyalty). Through OBBC (online-based-brand community).

The important thing that distinguishes this research is related to Prosustainability Network Quality. Augusty (2003) said that the aggregate measure generated through the accounting and

financial processes does not directly describe management activities, especially marketing management. Therefore, the measure used should be based on activities that can explain marketing activities. This study uses social media because to increase the competitiveness of the manufacturing industry, it is necessary to have a long-term sustainable relationship between customers and companies that are mutually beneficial, so that the problem of customer retention, customer satisfaction, product and service quality and cross-selling are important indicators that must be considered in the industry. In addition, this research develops by connecting social media to customer loyalty.

The aims of this study include: 1.) Does Social Media have a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty? 2.) Does Social Media have a positive and significant effect on Prosustainability Network Quality? 3.) Does Prosustainability Network Quality have a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty? 4.) Does Prosustainability Network Quality mediate the relationship between Social Media and Customer Loyalty?

Literature Review

Carla Martins, (2018) conducted an understanding of the antecedent contribution to Customer Loyalty, viewed from online communities and services. The results reveal that Social Media has a dual role as a community and an additional service. Consumers see Social Media as a way to express themselves and entertain themselves and also as a way to interact with and receive relevant information from sellers or companies. This study shows a positive influence in managing Social Media networks on their consumer loyalty and continues to improve studies on this so that consumers remain loyal in the future. Bickart and Schindler, (2001), consumers can perceive the information contained on Social Media about a product as a more credible source of information to support consumption or repeat purchase decisions. The study surveyed more than 1,000 industrial customers in Indonesia and social media engagement to measure the level of customer loyalty. The results show that using social media is directly related to increased loyalty. This study states that organizations can bring back dissatisfied customers and stakeholders through social media channels. Based on the previous explanation, the first hypothesis is:

H1: Social Media has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty.

Social Media apps have profoundly changed the way companies and customers interact. Communications used to be more effective, from company to customer, have become fully interactive among customers and between customers and companies (Farquhar & Rowley, 2006; Fisk et al., 2008; Hanna et al., 2011). Social Media has been widely used by many companies as the main channel for advertising and selling their products (Quevedo, 2012), the benefits of using Social Media are not only as a marketing platform, but the content shared can also increase engagement with consumers. Prosustainability Network Quality is a network between companies and their distribution channels. Companies can be successful if they have the power to build networks; this power is very important because only with good networking power can we choose the type of network, we can move the network in the direction we want and be able to accommodate our interests through a sales network that is external to the

company. The next role of Social Media is also in reflecting the user's self-image or other people and even an influencer, also supporting the Prosustainability Network Quality, namely the expansion of the network of relationships. Based on the previous description, the second hypothesis is:

H2: Social Media has a positive and significant effect on Prosustainability Network Quality.

In the research of Minna Saunila, Tero Rantala and Juhani Ukko, (2015), a network of relationships that is continuously maintained will increase the reputation and maintain the company's business continuity. Maintaining an effective company business network to increase Customer Loyalty and competitive advantage, the existing network can be maintained by always interacting and maintaining long-term relationships with customers, distributors, and company partners, to serve customers better. Based on the existing description, the third hypothesis is:

H3: Prosustainability Network Quality has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty

Social media use to increase the manufacturing industry's competitiveness requires a sustainable long-term relationship between customers and companies that are mutually beneficial, so that customer retention issues, customer satisfaction, product and service quality and cross-selling are important indicators that must be considered in the manufacturing industry. Third, develop by connecting Social Media to Customer Loyalty; many other companies already have social networks, but cannot develop their network sites. Companies need to understand how they can promote their network sites to attract and engage customers. Martins and Patrício (2013) found that the content of network sites tends to be largely self-contained by the company, and interactions between companies and customers are more frequent than interactions between customers. Thus, Customer Loyalty can be influenced through Prosustainability Network Quality by considering service concepts and methods with the application of Social Media, service approaches through social media, identifying, understanding and dimensions of Prosustainability Network Quality that can foster customer loyalty. Based on the existing description, the fourth hypothesis is:

H4: Prosustainability Network Quality mediates the relationship between Social Media and Customer Loyalty.

Methodology

Following the formulation of the problem and research objectives, this research design uses a quantitative approach (positivism) with an emphasis on explanatory research to explain causal relationships between variables through hypothesis testing (Sekaran, 2003). Cooper and Schindler (2006) reveal that research based on hypothesis testing to test a phenomenon that occurs is a type of explanatory research. The sample in this study is the distributor of BIG Champion sandpaper in Indonesia, which is active in the transaction process of as many as 300 distributors. As the main instrument in this study, which contains several closed questions that are described with a Likert scale. The questionnaires were distributed via e-mail and WhatsApp

distributors after the researchers asked for their willingness via random telephone contact or e-mail. The data analysis method used in this research is descriptive and statistical analysis, namely Smart PLS (Partial Least Square).

Results and Discussion

The object of this research is the sandpaper distributor from PT. Bahtera Indoampelas Gemilang, also known as the BIG Champion sandpaper brand. To see the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable and to test the hypotheses proposed in the study, structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis was used, which in this study used the Smart PLS 3.3.3 application. There are two main stages in SEM analysis with SmartPLS, namely the analysis of the outer model and the analysis of the inner model, which will be described later.

The second measure of convergent validity is the average variance extracted (AVE) value, where the variable is declared valid if the AVE value exceeds 0.5 (Hair et al., 2014). Based on the results of the loading factor and AVE above, it can be concluded that the four latent variable constructs have good validity ($AVE > 0.5$), which means that the information in each latent variable can be reflected through its manifest variable.

Table 1. Average Variance Extracted (Convergent Validity).

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
(X1) social media	0.534
(Y) Prosustainability	0.720
(Z) Customer Loyalty	0.663

Source: Data processed (2021)

The cross-loading value is obtained by comparing the magnitude of the relationship of each dimension to the variable, or as reflected by the factor loading value, with the magnitude of the relationship of each dimension to other variables. To get valid results, then the magnitude of the relationship of each dimension to the variable must be greater than the relationship of each dimension to the other variables. From the cross-loading table above, it is found that the factor loading of each dimension on the latent variable is proven to be greater than the relationship to the other latent variables, so that it can be concluded that discriminant validity is met. After the validity test is met, the next step will be to test the reliability of the measurement model by taking into account two criteria, namely Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability, which is obtained by looking at the output overview of the results of the SmartPLS algorithm. The recommended value to meet the reliability of the measurement structure is above 0.700 (Hair et al., 2014). The following are the results of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability tests on each research variable:

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha dan Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
(X1) social media	0.908	0.925
(Y) Prosustainability	0.905	0.934
(Z) Customer Loyalty	0.898	0.922

Source: Data processed (2021)

The table above shows that the results of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability are declared reliable where all variables have values that exceed the recommended values; this shows that the measurement model has good reliability. Based on the test results above, it can be stated that the measurement model is valid and reliable to meet the requirements for further analysis (inner model and hypothesis testing). R Square (R²) analysis was carried out on each endogenous latent variable which showed how much influence the endogenous latent variable received from each exogenous variable that contributed to it. The greater the value of R², the greater the influence received by the endogenous variables (Hair et al., 2014).

Table 3. R Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
(Y) Prosustainability	0.295	0.293
(Z) Customer Loyalty	0.661	0.658

Source: Data processed (2021)

Based on the table above, the variable (Y) Prosustainability is influenced by (X1) social media simultaneously at R² = 29.5%, and the remaining 70.5% is influenced by other variables outside the variables studied. The variable (Z) Customer Loyalty is influenced by (X1) social media simultaneously at R² = 66.1%, and the remaining 33.9% is influenced by other variables outside the variables studied. Hypothesis testing is used to test the presence or absence of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. In SmartPLS to, test the significance of the path coefficient using bootstrap with a significance level of 5%. The results of the calculations to test the hypothesis are presented in the following figures and tables:

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Description
X1 social media -> Y Prosustainability	0.544	0.550	0.050	10.840	0.000	Significant
X1 social media -> Z Customer Loyalty	0.258	0.268	0.123	2.102	0.036	Significant
Y Prosustainability -> Z Customer Loyalty	0.068	0.065	0.033	2.049	0.041	Significant
X1 social media -> Y Prosustainability -> Z Customer Loyalty	0.037	0.036	0.019	1.978	0.048	Significant

Source: Data processed (2021)

From testing the research results, there is a positive and significant influence of Social Media on Customer Loyalty at the distributor of PT. Bahtera Indoampas Gemilang. This is following the results of path coefficients with the original sample value, which shows a positive number with a t-count value greater than the t-table value and a smaller p-value, so it can be said that the Social Media variable has a positive and significant effect on the Customer variable. Loyalty. These results can be interpreted that a better the level of socialization or dissemination of information through digital that the distributor of PT has carried out. Bahtera Indoampas Gemilang affects the level of loyalty of the customers.

This study follows previous research, research conducted by (Rishipal, 2014) states that social media affects consumer loyalty, while according to (Chen & Yang, 2014) and (Nadeem, 2015) prove that social media can influence and build consumer loyalty; this means that the higher the use of social media by the distributor PT. Bahtera Indoampas Gemilang, the higher the loyalty given by the customers.

From testing the research results, there is a positive and significant influence between Social Media on Prosustainability and Network Quality on the distributor side of PT. Bahtera Indoampas Gemilang. This is following the results of path coefficients with the original sample value, which shows a positive number with a t-count value greater than the t-table value and a p-value less than 0.05 so that it can be said that the Social Media variable has a positive and significant effect on the variable. Prosustainability Network Quality.

From testing the research results, there is a positive and significant influence between Prosustainability Network Quality Media on Customer Loyalty at the distributor of PT. Bahtera Indoampas Gemilang. This is following the results of path coefficients with the original sample value, which shows a positive number with a t-count value greater than the t-table value and a p-value less than 0.05 so that it can be said that the Prosustainability Network Quality Media variable has a positive and significant effect. To the Customer Loyalty variable. The research results indicate a positive and significant influence on prosustainability network

quality, which mediates the relationship between social media and customer loyalty at PT. Bahtera Indoampas Gemilang. This is following the results of path coefficients with the original sample value, which shows a positive number with a t-count value greater than the t-table value and a p-value smaller than 0.05 so that it can be said that the prosustainability network quality variable mediates the relationship between social media and customer loyalty.

The results of this study are also in line with research conducted by Kurniawan and Herwoto (2017), where the results of his research show that there is a positive impact of using social media, one of which is Instagram, which makes it easier for respondents to be more effective in terms of time, effort and cost, each respondent feels. With this convenience, there is no need to bother renting a place, or looking for a place where they will promote their products; promotions can also be done anywhere and anytime they wish. Imron (2018) also states that there is a joint impact between social media variables, namely popular content, relevant content, profitable campaigns, and the frequency of updating content on consumer loyalty. With promotion through social media, it can be seen that there is an increase in consumer enthusiasm so that it is profitable for the company, and in the end, it will form high consumer loyalty.

This section discusses the contributions obtained from this research, both theoretically and practically. This study's results can contribute to scientific development, especially in the field of Marketing Management. The results of this study can be used as a consideration for both business entities and educational institutions to develop marketing strategies, increase sales turnover, and maintain a sustainable company by adapting to technological developments. The results of this study can be used as reference material for business people on how to create a good, closer and healthier network of cooperation for the sake of the company's future sustainability. Moreover, when applied, the results of this research will build a relationship of trust so that new business opportunities will open, and it will be easier to offer products/services and provide more benefits.

Theoretically, the contribution of research in several ways regarding customer loyalty, namely:

1. This study develops the Theory of Network, proposed by Durkheim and Tonnies (1890), that people tend to think and behave the same way because they are connected. With the view that the network system as a whole can be used to interpret the behavior of the people involved (Mitchell, 1969; Tichy, Tushman & Fombrun, 1979). The result of this study is that the role of social media can foster a sense of loyalty mediated by prosustainability network quality, following the concept of Network Theory, is a healthy sales network that is always obedient to sales conditions with more ability to recruit potential customers.
2. Social Media, used as one of the variables in this research, is a tool in applying digital customer relationship management; its use has a significant relationship with customer loyalty. This study is one of the few empirical investigations into relationship marketing based on social media communication in the B2B concept. These results follow Asril's (2021) research on relationship marketing in the B2B concept, social media that affects

customer loyalty in a B2B environment; the relationship quality aspect of social media services is positively related to customer loyalty.

The results of this study provide practical contributions in several ways regarding customer loyalty, namely:

1. This study shows that the success of the marketing strategy implemented by the company through social media that is used intensely can influence and build the loyalty of sandpaper distributors; social media has an important role in developing marketing strategies within the company and influencing consumers to buy products online, Liang & Turban (2011). Social media can affect consumer loyalty, Rishipal (2014). Then according to research (Chang, HH., 2009) and (Nadeem, 2015), social media will be able to influence and build consumer loyalty because social media is related to marketing strategies.
2. This study proves that the sustainability of network quality which mediates social media variables on customer loyalty, does have a significant effect. Building a good business network will help increase relationships, improve business quality, and gain more trust amid competition with competitors, ultimately creating distributor loyalty to sandpaper companies and increasing sales turnover.

Conclusion

This study draws several conclusions to test the effect of social media, on customer loyalty through the mediating role of prosustainability network quality. Based on the results of the research, discussion, research findings and referring to the theory, it can be concluded that the results of the research, it can be seen that:

1. Social Media has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty; determining the right marketing strategy through social media will increase and maintain the number of consumers to remain loyal in buying products, be active and respond quickly with social media that is applied has an important role to develop marketing strategies in the company and affect the loyalty of the industrial sandpaper company distributors.
2. Social Media has a positive and significant impact on Prosustainability. Network Quality, continuing to expand business networks will help the success of marketing development strategies; social media is very effective for strengthening and adding to business networks, determining business flows and ultimately increasing profits. Attractive promotions regularly, regular evaluations and maximum service through social media can create different things to survive and compete with similar competitors.
3. Based on the results of hypothesis 3 test on testing the effect of Prosustainability Network Quality on Customer Loyalty, it can be said that the Prosustainability Network Quality variable has a positive and significant effect on the Customer Loyalty variable. Therefore, in conclusion, H3 is accepted, which reads that Prosustainability Network Quality Media has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty.

4. Based on the results of hypothesis 4 testing on the Prosustainability Network Quality test, which mediates the relationship between Social Media and Customer Loyalty, the conclusion is H4 is accepted, which reads Prosustainability Network Quality mediates the relationship between Social Media and Customer Loyalty.

Based on the results of the research conducted, the suggestion for the company is that PT. Bahtera Indoampas Gemilang further improves communication on its services with consumers in an excellent, fast and responsive manner through Social Media PT. Bahtera Indoampas Gemilang can develop its online store site on other social media and increase its promotion not only through internet media, but also expand its promotion through print and electronic media so that many consumers know about PT. Bahtera Indoampas Gemilang and its site. For further researchers, they should be able to expand the sample and object of research as a generalization of the results of this study, for example, on all online store sites in Indonesia, so that this research has a wider area. The next research is recommended to conduct a mixed-method research method such as direct interviews with customers who feel the company's experience and distributing questionnaires to enrich the research results. Further researchers should be able to add other variables or other factors that are still related to this research, such as website quality, risk perception, and e-service, to find out other aspects that can increase consumer loyalty.

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